

In Press, World Futures

Cluster Analysis of Features Associated with Unidentified Anomalous Phenomena
Described in 216 Select Reports from 1947-2016

Stephen Bruehl^{1,2}, Sarah Little², and Robert M. Powell²

¹Department of Anesthesiology, Vanderbilt University Medical Center, Nashville, TN

²Scientific Coalition for UAP Studies, Town Lake Dr., Ste A, #173, Fort Myers, Florida.

Corresponding Author: Stephen Bruehl, Ph.D., Scientific Coalition for UAP Studies,
Town Lake Dr., Ste A, #173, Fort Myers, Florida. E-mail: Stephen.bruehl@vumc.org

Word Count (text): 7,349 words

Abstract

Patterns in reported characteristics of unidentified anomalous phenomena (UAP) in historical databases can be statistically examined to gain insights into distinct types of reported UAP. We applied cluster analysis to the UAP report database created by Powell et al. (2023) that applied strict selection criteria to witness reports in several historical databases. They identified $n = 301$ UAP reports likely to represent true anomalous phenomena and manually grouped them into classes based on shape. Here we examined a subsample of $n=216$ of these reports containing complete data necessary to conduct cluster analysis. We targeted five reported UAP features described in that previous work: shape, estimated size, ability to hover, presence of electromagnetic (EM) effects, and presence of sound. The two-step clustering algorithm identified seven distinct clusters, with this model of good statistical quality (silhouette value = 0.6). Object shape was the strongest driver of clustering results although other features contributed. For example, two distinct clusters were characterized primarily by absence of hovering (potentially reflecting unique reporting sources) and two distinct clusters comprised objects all exhibiting either: 1) EM effects (disc/sphere or ovoid) or 2) sound (unassociated with shape). Of the objects exhibiting EM effects, 97% were viewed at estimated distances of $\leq 2,000$ feet from the observer. Similarities to and differences from manual classification results of Powell et al. were noted. Findings suggest that statistical pattern recognition techniques like cluster analysis can extract meaningful information from high quality witness report data that could improve understanding of the nature of UAP.

Keywords: Unidentified Anomalous Phenomena; UAP; Pattern Recognition; Cluster Analysis; Typology; Characteristics

Introduction

Unidentified anomalous phenomena (UAP) described in the hundreds of thousands of witness reports comprising the published UAP literature and UAP reporting databases are associated with a wide variety of shapes and features (Powell et al., 2023). Although certain shapes (e.g., discs, triangles) and characteristics (e.g., electromagnetic [EM] effects, odd movement patterns, no sound) tend to recur, the variety of reported UAP features and the number of possible feature combinations make it challenging to identify commonalities across sightings that might help advance knowledge regarding the nature of UAP. Efforts to discern a typology of characteristics found in UAP reports have been almost exclusively unidimensional in character, for example, based solely on reported object shape or luminosity (e.g., daylight disk vs. nocturnal lights [Hynek, 1972; Teodorani, 2004]) or on reported distance from the observer (e.g. close encounters; [Hynek, 1972]). These unidimensional approaches fail to acknowledge that profiles reflecting combinations of multiple features might be more informative as a means of classifying the physical characteristics and object behaviors found in UAP reports into functional types that could be used for generating potentially testable hypotheses.

Historically, analyses of characteristics of UAP from witness report databases suffer from two major problems: poor data and poor methodology. Most public databases are filled with reports that are either of objects identifiable *a posteriori* (e.g. Starlink, the planet Venus), are information poor (they are missing key metrics like distance, location, time of day, direction of sighting, size, shape, color, etc.), or the information given is of poor quality (e.g. incorrect distance estimates leading to incorrect size, speed, acceleration, luminosity, etc.).

Examples of good methodology applied to poor-quality data include sophisticated statistical methodologies used to examine the NUFORC public database of raw UAP reports. For example, patterns in and factors influencing the geographic locations of reported UAP sightings have been examined based on analysis of ~48,000 compiled witness reports using

mixed effects linear regression (Watters et al., 2023) and ~99,000 compiled witness reports using Bayesian small area estimation (Medina et al., 2023). Although these methodologies are sound, it is not possible to draw firm conclusions about the spatio-temporal frequency of anomalous aerial phenomena from these studies due to limitations in the data.

To address the problem of poor data, this study turned to the select dataset of Powell et al. (2023). These authors screened 100,000 witness reports of UAP observed between 1947 and 2016 contained in publicly-available government (Blue Book, GEIPAN) and civilian UAP databases (NICAP, CUFOSS, MUFON). Each report was individually reviewed using a methodology that specified reliability of witness testimonies, object angular size greater than 0.15 degrees, sufficient lighting, and sufficient information detail (see Powell et al., 2023 for methodological details). The purpose of these criteria was to create a dataset of UAP reports that maximized robust information and minimized false-positives, that is, the goal was for all the objects to be real objects, clearly seen and well-described by those who witnessed them, and not identifiable by either the witness or the post-hoc investigator. These semi-quantitative selection criteria resulted in a final sample ($n = 301$) of UAP cases judged likely to reflect true anomalous objects.

Powell et al. then manually collated the reported physical characteristics, grouped reports by shape, and tallied the following key characteristics: estimated size, kinematics (ability to hover, maximum speed, acceleration, odd motion), presence of EM effects, and presence of sound. They *a priori* defined one class of anomalous object to be those that, within a given report, were described as displaying hovering + exhibiting extreme speed + producing no sound. From their tallies, they also found that objects reported as “triangles” were consistently observed to hover but were not associated with EM effects or sound. Because of the robustness of the underlying dataset, these findings are informative and a useful qualitative step towards developing an empirically-supported UAP typology. However, the methodology they used to

determine UAP type classes is limited in scope and prone to bias. Although their tallies are quantitative, their selection of shape as the key characteristic and their definition of a class of anomalous objects are based on prior, qualitative inferences about UAP witness reports and the objects that underlie them. This does not make their choices incorrect, but it makes them biased by expectations. In fact, these authors suggested that future UAP research employ unbiased statistical algorithms to identify commonalities in UAP report characteristics that might otherwise be overlooked.

We turn here to cluster analysis, a well-established statistical pattern recognition technique (Everitt et al., 2001) that employs various algorithms to classify objects based on patterns of covariation in a set of targeted features, such that objects assigned to the same cluster are more similar to each other than they are to objects in other clusters. For example, in the biomedical context, cluster analysis has been applied to patients' descriptions of headache symptoms, with results statistically confirming widespread clinical assumptions regarding the existence of two distinct headache types (migraine and tension-type headache) that are each associated with very different combinations of symptoms (Bruehl et al., 1999). In the UAP context, cluster analysis can be used to statistically identify distinct UAP types (clusters) based on patterns of UAP characteristics in witness reports with minimal influence of prior assumptions or expectations (the only assumption is in the features chosen on which to perform the cluster analysis). By working with the same underlying dataset used by Powell et al., we can compare and contrast the UAP type classes from manual analysis with those from statistical pattern recognition.

To our knowledge, no published studies have used cluster analysis to quantitatively determine whether there are distinct, empirically-supported UAP types discernable within witness report data. Therefore, the current study was intended to be a methodological proof of

concept to test the potential value of using cluster analysis to extract meaningful information from UAP witness report data.

Materials and Methods

Data

As described in and provided by Powell et al. (2023), our sample starts with a publicly-available Excel database of 301 best-case UAP witness reports of anomalous aerial objects that were hand-selected from multiple large databases using the following criteria: reliability of witness testimonies, object angular size greater than 0.15 degrees, sufficient lighting, and sufficient information detail. In the current study, while we tested a variety of possible clustering models (detailed in the Statistical Analysis section below), the final cluster analysis detailed here focuses on five reported UAP characteristics targeted in that prior work: shape (but here categorized as disc/sphere, ovoid, cylindrical, broadly triangular, and other), estimated size, ability to hover, presence of EM effects, and presence of sound. These five primary UAP characteristics were the variables used for determination of the clusters. The UAP database created by Powell et al. also contained a variety of secondary sighting and object characteristics extracted from witness reports that were not used to create the clusters but which can be examined after the clusters have been derived to aid in their characterization (listed in Table 3). Estimated size as well as the secondary characteristics of distance from the observer and estimated altitude were continuous variables in feet. All other variables were categorical.

Data Verification and Modification

The original Excel data file used by Powell et al. (2023) was imported into the statistical software package to be used for all analyses (IBM® SPSS® for Windows Version 29). Each UAP case in the imported file was then checked for accuracy against the original Excel file. In order for cluster analysis to be performed, all UAP cases included in the analyzed sample were required to have non-missing values for the five UAP characteristics that were specified as the

primary clustering variables. Because 85 cases in the original Excel file were missing data on either estimated object size (n= 81) and/or were missing a defined object shape (unknown shape or light in the sky; n=16), these cases were excluded from the cluster analysis. From the original n = 301 cases, a final sample of n = 216 cases was selected to analyze.

Dichotomous UAP characteristics were recoded such that characteristics noted by witnesses to be present during the sighting were coded as 1 and characteristics not explicitly mentioned in the witness report were coded as 0. In the case of the category of sound, this collapsed the original three categories (“sound reported”, “sound reported as absent” and “no sound reported”) to two categories, sound or no sound. A single dichotomous composite variable (coded as 1/0 for present/absent) capturing apparent odd movement patterns was derived based on whether the sighting report indicated presence of at least one of the following movement characteristics: angular movement; presence of wobbling, falling leaf, or zig zag motions; or spinning of the object in flight. To control variability due to the variety of shape words used to describe potentially identical UAP forms, the shape variable was categorized prior to analysis into five broad categories: Disc/Sphere, Ovoid, Triangle/Delta/Boomerang, Cylindrical, and Other (e.g., rectangular, barbell, cube, “other”; n=5). These shape categories were dummy-coded as 1-5 for analyses. The original Powell et al. (2023) dataset from which the current analyzed dataset of n=216 cases was drawn is available at: <https://zenodo.org/records/10287332>.

Statistical Analyses

Analyses were performed using the two-step cluster analysis procedure in IBM® SPSS® for Windows Version 29 (IBM; Armonk, New York). There are several different cluster analysis procedures available, including hierarchical cluster analysis, K-means cluster analysis, and two-step cluster analysis. The first two procedures have the significant disadvantage of requiring the researchers to use their judgment to determine the optimal number of clusters to be extracted, a feature that potentially introduces the same forms of bias that are associated with manual

analysis. We therefore chose to use a relatively newer technique, two-step cluster analysis (Chiu et al., 2001; Kent et al., 2014). This approach is entirely data-driven and automatically selects the optimal number of clusters based solely on characteristics of the data. This automated statistical cluster selection avoids potential bias in cluster selection related to prior expectations. Two-step cluster analysis also permits simultaneous inclusion of both continuous (e.g. size) and categorical (e.g. EM effects) variables as required for the present study. In the current work, the two-step cluster analysis employed the log-likelihood distance measure for determining clusters given that both categorical and continuous variables were included. Schwarz's Bayesian Information Criterion (BIC) was used to determine the optimal number of clusters.

It was assumed that the witness report data we are examining likely includes substantial error from misestimations of some values (e.g., size, distance) as well as misperceptions (e.g., shape, flight behavior). Given this situation, cluster analysis was expected to be successful in identifying distinct, high quality UAP clusters to the extent that the UAP signal exceeded the inherent noise in the witness reports. In contrast, if the UAP case data were largely random and reflected primarily statistical noise, cluster analysis would be unable to identify distinct and coherent UAP types. Stated formally, the two-step cluster analysis we performed assumed that meaningful clusters exist within the data and compared a null hypothesis against an alternative hypothesis as follows:

- Null Hypothesis (H_0): There is no meaningful clustering in the data, and all observations belong to one homogenous group.
- Alternative Hypothesis (H_1): There are distinct clusters within the dataset, with each cluster representing a cohesive subgroup of observations that are significantly different from other clusters.

The quality of clustering models is evaluated based on the average silhouette value obtained (Hubert & Arabie, 1985; Jain & Dubes, 1988; Rousseeuw, 1987; Kaufman & Rousseeuw, 1990). The silhouette value is calculated for each case by comparing the average distance between an object and all other objects in the same cluster (a) with the average distance between that object and all objects in the nearest neighboring cluster (b). The silhouette value (s) is calculated as: $s = (b - a) / \max(a, b)$. Thus, the silhouette value is a measure of how similar an object is to its own cluster (cohesion) compared to other clusters (separation). Values can range from -1 to +1, with a high positive value indicating that the object is well matched to its own cluster and poorly matched to neighboring clusters. A cluster analysis producing an average silhouette value of 0.50 or greater indicates a good clustering model, reflecting clusters that are cohesive within themselves (i.e., cases within each cluster group together strongly based on the characteristics examined) and that the clusters have good separation (i.e., the clusters are highly distinct from each other). Silhouette values < 0.50 indicate an inadequate clustering model. To conservatively guard against the possibility that our clustering results reported below might simply reflect type I error, we also ran two-step cluster analyses like those described below on 30 simulated datasets comprising random data for the five clustering variables targeted (with similar variable coding and ranges). All of these cluster analyses produced a silhouette score $< .50$ indicating inadequate cluster quality as expected with random data. Moreover, the variable identified as the most important for determining the clustering solutions across these analyses varied substantially and appeared random (see Appendix 1 for details).

In preliminary analyses, we tested a series of models reflecting slightly different sets of clustering variables to determine which one led to the best model quality in terms of silhouette value. Our starting point was a model including the following five UAP characteristics that were examined in Powell et al.: object shape (using the 5 broad categories described above), estimated size, EM effects, presence of sound, and hovering. Hovering was chosen to index kinematic

features in this initial model because it can be readily identified even in the absence of accurate size and distance estimates that are needed to accurately judge other kinematic characteristics (e.g., maximum speed, extreme acceleration, unusual kinematic range). In subsequent models, we added to this initial model the other kinematic features reported by Powell et al. (odd movement, speed > Mach 1, and instantaneous acceleration/deceleration) individually and in combination. Finally, we re-ran all of the clustering models above using a larger set of more specific shape categories like that identified by Powell et al. (disc/circular, sphere/round, boomerang, cylinder/cigar, oval/egg/football, ellipse, bullet, cone, lozenge, delta/triangle, Saturn-shaped, diamond, quadrilateral, barbell). Results of this series of analyses indicated that the highest quality clustering model (i.e., largest silhouette score) was the relatively simple initial model described above: shape (Disc/Sphere, Ovoid, Triangular/Boomerang/Chevron, Cylindrical, or Other), hovering (0 = Absent, 1 = Present), EM effects (0 = Absent, 1 = Present), sound (0 = Absent, 1 = Present), and estimated object size (continuous variable in feet). This model is the focus of the detailed results described below.

The cluster to which each individual UAP report was automatically assigned during the cluster analysis (based on similarity to the overall feature profile of each cluster) was saved as a variable reflecting cluster membership for use in subsequent analyses. Given general agreement that a minimum sample size of $n=10$ cases per clustering variable is needed for stable cluster analysis results, the current sample of $n = 216$ UAP cases was more than sufficient for clustering based on the 5 variables included in the final model.

Statistical comparisons between the derived clusters on the five primary clustering variables and the associated secondary characteristics described above were carried out to aid in characterizing the resulting clusters. All continuous variables (size, altitude, distance) significantly violated normality assumptions. Therefore, statistical comparisons between clusters for continuous variables employed nonparametric median tests, with post-hoc pairwise

comparisons (unadjusted p values). Chi-square analyses were used for all pairwise comparisons for categorical variables. We used a two-sided probability value of $p < .05$ as the criterion for statistical significance. We note that tests of the statistical significance of differences between clusters on the five primary variables used to create the clusters are inherently biased by the fact that the clustering algorithm was designed to maximize differences between clusters on these features. Significant differences between clusters on secondary UAP characteristics available for analysis (i.e., those not included in the cluster analysis; described in Table 3) are not biased in this manner.

Results

Sample Characteristics

Summary statistics for the analyzed sample ($n=216$) regarding primary UAP features used in the cluster analysis are presented in Table 1. A disc/spherical shape was most commonly reported, reflecting nearly half of the cases examined. The majority of reports (59.7%) described an object displaying the ability to hover. Presence of sound or EM effects associated with UAP were each noted to occur in less than 20% of cases in the analyzed sample.

Cluster Analysis

The two-step cluster analysis with automated clustering identified seven clusters. The mean silhouette value of this cluster model was 0.6, indicating good quality clustering with clusters that were both cohesive within clusters and distinct between clusters. The importance of each UAP feature for determining cluster membership is portrayed graphically in Figure 1. Importance values in this figure are automatically generated within the two-step cluster analysis procedure and are based on a series of statistical comparisons of differences between features for each cluster, with the average $-\log_{10}$ p-value for each feature across clusters considered to be a measure of feature importance (rescaled so that the greatest observed value is 1). Shape was the most important determinant of how UAP reports were clustered while estimated size was the

least important. Analyses described in Appendix 1 suggest that the identification of UAP shape as the most important cluster determinant in the analysis above was not biased by differences in the characteristics (categorical variable ranging from 1-5 rather than a continuous or dichotomous variable) or distribution (e.g., uniform versus Poisson) of the shape variable relative to the other four primary clustering variables.

Profiles of Key Distinguishing UAP Characteristics for Each Cluster

We present general descriptions of key features in UAP reports that characterize each identified cluster below, and our detailed findings are summarized in Table 2 (for UAP characteristics used as primary clustering variables) and Table 3 (for secondary UAP characteristics).

Cluster 1

In terms of clustering variables, Cluster 1 consisted entirely of reports of objects described as disc/spherical in shape. These were of moderate size relative to the range of UAP sizes in our analyzed sample and all displayed the ability to hover. None of the UAP in this cluster were associated with sound or EM effects. In terms of secondary characteristics, sightings of these UAP were equally likely to occur during the day or at night and apparent domes were reported more often than in descriptions of disc/spherical-shaped UAP in any other cluster. These UAP were typically viewed at close range and near the ground, and they were the most likely UAP type to display odd movement patterns (e.g., angular motion, wobbling, and/or falling leaf).

Cluster 2

UAP assigned to Cluster 2 exhibited many similar characteristics to those in Cluster 1. Regarding clustering variables, objects in Cluster 2 were all disc/spherical in shape, of moderate size relative to other clusters, and were not associated with sound or EM effects. However, unlike UAP in Cluster 1, no objects in Cluster 2 were reported to hover. Notably, 56.8% of reports in Cluster 2 were made by pilots while in flight compared to 15.6% of reports in Cluster

1 which was also comprised entirely of disc/spherical objects. Consistent with the high frequency of objects viewed in-flight in Cluster 2, these UAP were observed at a notably higher altitude and greater distance from the observer than all other cluster-derived UAP types. This relatively greater viewing distance is likely to have influenced the pattern of features reported for UAP assigned to this cluster. In terms of other secondary characteristics, objects in Cluster 2 frequently displayed odd movement patterns, were more likely to be seen during the day (76% vs. 52% for Cluster 1), to be detected on radar, and to appear with multiple objects simultaneously. Cluster 2 exhibited the highest rate of multiple UAP of all identified clusters. Perhaps not surprising given the frequency of daytime sightings in Cluster 2, distinct lights were much less frequently observed on UAP assigned to Cluster 2 than Cluster 1 (or any other cluster).

Cluster 3

Two key distinguishing features were noted for the primary clustering variables in Cluster 3. Objects in this cluster were distinguished from all other cluster-derived UAP types by the fact that they consisted almost entirely of cylindrical objects (e.g., cylinder, cigar, bullet). Objects in this cluster also displayed the largest size of any of the cluster-derived UAP type (see Table 1). Approximately half of these UAP displayed the ability to hover. Regarding secondary characteristics, objects in Cluster 3 were the least likely to display odd movement patterns of any identified UAP type and were also the least likely to display instantaneous acceleration/deceleration or instantaneous direction changes. Objects in Cluster 3 also tended most often to be seen while in the air, at a median estimated altitude of 1500 feet, with two-thirds sighted at night. These UAP were the most likely of all cluster-derived UAP types to reportedly respond to observer's actions (e.g., appear to play "cat and mouse" with a moving automobile).

Cluster 4

The most notable feature regarding the primary clustering variables for Cluster 4 was shape, with these UAP reported most frequently to be roughly triangular in shape (e.g., triangle, delta, boomerang, chevron). All objects in this cluster displayed an ability to hover, none were associated with EM effects or sound, and they were intermediate in size relative to other clusters. In terms of secondary characteristics, objects in Cluster 4 tended to be observed at low altitudes and relatively near the observer. It is notable that nearly all sightings of UAP assigned to Cluster 4 took place at night (92%) and black was the single most common object color reported (32%). In more than two-thirds of these cases the UAP displayed distinct lights, a higher percentage than any other cluster type. Objects in Cluster 4 were more likely than all other identified UAP types to exhibit estimated speeds greater than Mach 1 and instantaneous acceleration/deceleration. More than 40% displayed odd movement patterns and approached the observer.

Cluster 5

UAP in Cluster 5 were distributed relatively equally between objects described as roughly triangular and those described as ovoid (e.g., oval, egg, football). Beyond shape, findings for the other clustering variables indicated that objects in Cluster 5 exhibited the same relatively smaller estimated size as objects in Cluster 2 (median of 40 feet). None were described as hovering nor were any associated with sound or EM effects. Regarding secondary characteristics, UAP assigned to Cluster 5 tended to be seen in the air yet appeared largely to demonstrate slow movement and no unusual acceleration. Compared to most other clusters, objects in Cluster 5 less frequently exhibited speeds > Mach 1, although as noted above were not reported in any cases to hover. Odd movement patterns were relatively rare in this type of UAP. Finally, objects in this cluster were less likely than those in all other clusters to approach the observer.

Cluster 6

Regarding the clustering variables, the key characteristic defining all objects assigned to Cluster 6 was the presence of EM effects; this attribute was *only* observed in objects assigned to this cluster. Cluster 6 was also one of only two clusters in which UAP were associated with sound, although this was noted only in a minority of cases in this cluster. Of the UAP assigned to Cluster 6, 72% were described as disc/spherical or ovoid in shape. More than half of reported objects in this cluster displayed the ability to hover.

Given that EM effects were limited to objects assigned to this one cluster, the most relevant finding for secondary characteristics may be that UAP assigned to Cluster 6 were typically seen at relatively close range and at low altitudes. Excluding one extreme outlier in estimated distance (20,000 feet), 97.0% of the UAP in Cluster 6, all of which exhibited EM effects, were viewed at an estimated distance of 2,000 feet or less from the observer (and 90.9% of these UAP were estimated to be 1,500 feet or less from the observer). Nearly half of the cases assigned to this cluster included reports of odd movement patterns, and objects of this type were more likely than all other identified UAP types to approach and engage actively with the observer according to the reports. Half of the sightings in Cluster 6 took place at night and nearly half of the objects were described as having a metallic appearance. Reactions by animals to the UAP were the most common in this cluster (8.3%) although rates of this feature were low across all clusters.

Cluster 7

In terms of clustering variables, UAP assigned to Cluster 7 were noted to exhibit the widest variety of shapes, with disc/sphere, ovoid, broadly triangular, and cylindrical shapes all being relatively common. Most of these objects exhibited an ability to hover and their typical size was intermediate relative to other clusters. Objects in Cluster 7 were distinguished from other UAP types by the presence of sound associated with all objects in this cluster. Of the secondary features, the most notable finding (given the association of objects in all of these

reports with sound) are that objects assigned to Cluster 7 were most frequently seen near the observer and near ground level. UAP in Cluster 7 were also the least likely to display estimated speeds $>$ Mach 1 and none displayed an apparent acceleration greater than 10 g-forces. More than three-quarters of the objects in this category of sightings were observed at night and approximately two-thirds exhibited distinct lighting.

We tested the possibility of bias in Cluster 7 related to our assumption that no specific mention of sound in the witness report indicated the absence of sound. A follow-up sensitivity analysis suggested that the primary cluster results were not biased, given that objects in Cluster 7 also differed from all other identified UAP types on the *confirmed* presence of sound when analyses were restricted to the smaller number of witness reports that specifically indicated presence vs. absence of sound. When restricted to this subset of cases, the pattern of features noted above characterizing Cluster 7 compared to the other clusters remained quite similar.

Lighting Characteristics of UAP Observed at Night by Cluster

In additional follow-up analyses, we restricted the witness reports to only those occurring at night in order to examine lighting features in a context when lights are most likely to be visible. We briefly highlight some relevant findings. UAP in Clusters 4 (roughly triangular) and 7 (associated with sound) were the most likely to display distinct lights during nighttime sightings (76.5% and 73.9% respectively). In contrast, UAP in Cluster 5 were the least likely to display distinct lights at night (25.0%). We then narrowed our focus further to nighttime sighting reports in which distinct lights were reported (n=67). Red was the most common color, noted in over 57% of objects assigned to Clusters 1, 4, 6, and 7. Distinct white lights were the next most common coloration in this sighting context, reported to be present in 50% or more of objects assigned to all clusters except Cluster 5. In 10 of 26 (38.5%) of nighttime sightings of roughly triangular UAP (Cluster 4), the objects displayed both red and white lights simultaneously. Beyond red and white, blue/purple was the most common color of distinct lights, associated most

frequently with the disc/spherical objects in Cluster 1 (37.5%) and objects displaying EM effects in Cluster 6 (33.3%). Objects in Clusters 6 (UAP associated with EM effects) and 7 (UAPs associated with sound) were the most likely to display a light beam when viewed at night (12.5% and 17.4%, respectively).

Statistical Comparisons of UAP Characteristics by Cluster

Statistical comparisons between clusters regarding differences in reported UAP features are summarized in Tables 4 (for primary clustering variables) and 5 (other secondary UAP characteristics), respectively. Statistically significant differences that appear most interpretable or meaningful are highlighted in the rightmost column of both tables. Beyond these comparisons, we also conducted secondary analyses testing for possible differences in age of the sighting reports between clusters (based on medians expressed as Julian day counts).

Distributions of sighting year by cluster are summarized visually in Figure 2. Testing of pairwise differences between clusters indicated that sightings in Cluster 4 (roughly triangular) were significantly more recent than those in most other clusters (Clusters 1, 2, 5, and 6), an effect driven by reports of true triangles and boomerang-shaped UAP (see below). Sightings in Clusters 2 and 5, both of which reflected objects viewed at greater distances and at higher altitudes in the absence of hovering, were significantly older than those in Clusters 1, 6, and 7. All other comparisons between clusters regarding age of the sightings were nonsignificant.

This study was intended in part to evaluate the extent to which our statistical findings would correspond with the manual analysis by Powell et al. (2023). We therefore evaluated whether sighting age within two specific clusters differed as a function of the more specific shape categorizations used in this latter study. Shape distributions according to the Powell et al. (2023) categories are color-coded for each statistical cluster in Figure 2. Within Cluster 1, we found that the age of sighting reports describing a round/spherical object versus a disc-shaped object was not significantly different ($p > .10$). Similar comparisons within Cluster 2 which also

reflected only disc-shaped/spherical objects also did not reveal any significant differences in sighting age ($p > .10$). In contrast, significant changes over time in specific UAP shape descriptions based on the Powell et al. categorizations were noted within the cluster reflecting the highest proportion of objects roughly triangular in shape (Cluster 4). As is evident from inspection of Figure 2, objects in Powell et al.'s delta/chevron category (e.g., a flying wing) were significantly older than reports of objects in their triangular ($p < .01$) or boomerang categories ($p < 0.05$). Triangular and boomerang categories were statistically similar in age ($p > .10$).

Discussion

This study revealed for the first time that cluster analysis, a statistical pattern recognition technique that is unbiased by *a priori* assumptions about UAP types, was able to identify several statistically-distinct UAP archetypes noted to recur frequently in the UAP case literature. These UAP archetypes include: 1) the silent black triangular object seen at night which exhibits distinct red and white lights and is often observed hovering yet can accelerate rapidly (Marler et al., 2013); 2) the “daylight disc” reported by pilots to be seen in flight at greater distance and altitude and often captured on radar (Hynek, 1972); and 3) the classic saucer-shaped UAP (sometimes with a dome) typically seen relatively close to the observer near the ground that silently hovers and moves in odd ways (e.g., “falling leaf” motion, wobbling). Broadly, our results supported the focus of Powell et al. on shape as the primary distinguishing feature of apparent UAP types, and indeed, shape was statistically the strongest determinant of cluster membership in this study. However, other UAP features including ability to hover, presence of EM effects or sound, and to a lesser extent, estimated object size, all contribute to statistical classification of UAP types. The fact that the clustering algorithm was able to identify distinct UAP types based on multiple characteristics and that these clustering results were statistically-determined to be of good quality (i.e., silhouette value $> .50$) are a proof of concept indicating that it is possible to extract meaningful information from UAP witness report data that are of high quality. Given these

results, additional research applying both cluster analysis and machine-learning approaches to identify patterns in larger, well-curated UAP sighting datasets could lead to meaningful advances in our understanding of UAP. Whether this type of statistical approach could be similarly successful if applied to less structured, uncleaned UAP databases (e.g., NUFORC) remains to be proven.

Beyond the broad implications above, several specific findings of our cluster analysis warrant mention. The characteristics of the statistically-identified UAP clusters can be examined in the context of current aviation propulsion technology and capabilities. Known propulsion methods for fixed wing aircraft permit high (transonic) speeds (military jet aircraft) and hovering for brief periods (F22/F35, Harrier). Helicopters can hover for extended periods, although are not capable of rapid acceleration or speeds approaching Mach 1. For both traditional fixed wing aircraft and helicopters, these flight characteristics are only achieved using propulsion systems that create high noise levels that are unlikely to be missed if associated with a UAP sighting. Drones produce noise although in many cases at lower noise levels than other aircraft, they can hover for extended periods (depending on the energy source), and in some cases may achieve speeds as high as a modern jet (e.g., the B21 can become a drone piloted by AI). Lighter than air craft (e.g., blimps, ballons) may hover silently, but are unable to fly at high speeds or exhibit high acceleration. Taken together, objects that can both silently hover and silently accelerate very rapidly to transonic speeds do not fit the profile of any currently known aviation propulsion technology.

The UAP type identified in the current study that was characterized specifically by presence of sound (Cluster 7) might be hypothesized based on current propulsion technology to display the greatest speeds and kinematic range if that UAP sound were propulsion related. Contrary to this hypothesis, the UAP type defined by presence of sound (Cluster 7), while often observed hovering, was the least likely of all identified UAP types to display speeds > Mach 1.

Conversely, UAP assigned to Clusters 1 and 4, which were seen relatively near the observers but not associated with sound, were reported not only to uniformly hover, but also frequently exhibit odd movement patterns, instant acceleration/deceleration, and/or transonic speeds. For example, when examined at the level of individual UAP reports, 32.9% of the objects assigned to Clusters 1 and 4 hovered silently but also displayed either instant acceleration/deceleration or speeds > Mach 1. The extreme kinematic range reported in many UAP reports assigned to these clusters in the total absence of any sound suggests that these flight characteristics are not likely achieved via traditional aircraft propulsion methods.

The manual analysis by Powell et al. (2023) had concluded that triangular craft were the most likely shape to exhibit an unusual kinematic range, that is, both hovering and exhibiting very high speeds often with extreme acceleration. Our cluster analysis results without any *a priori* assumptions are consistent with this conclusion. UAP assigned to Cluster 4 were broadly triangular in shape, all were observed to hover, and they exhibited instant acceleration/deceleration and high speeds (>Mach 1) more often than objects in any other cluster (with several such comparisons reaching statistical significance).

In contrast to the situation described above, UAP in Cluster 5 only rarely displayed features and flight characteristics that appear notably different from those associated with current aviation technology. One commonality that UAP in Cluster 5 shared with Cluster 2 was that UAP in both clusters tended to be seen at greater distances and higher altitudes than UAP in other clusters. These sighting characteristics may have contributed to the absence of EM effects and sound reported in objects assigned to these clusters. UAP in Cluster 5 were almost always ovoid or broadly triangular in shape with their key defining characteristic being the absence of hovering. They were also the most likely of all UAP types identified to exhibit some form of external structure on the UAP (e.g., windows, unusual external shapes). These features suggest

that Cluster 5 is the most likely cluster to represent unusual or not-easily-identified human-made craft.

The critical feature distinguishing UAP assigned to Cluster 7 from all other UAP types was the presence of sound associated with all objects in that cluster. It is notable that UAP in Cluster 7 were relatively evenly distributed between disc/sphere, ovoid, triangular, and cylinder shapes. While the reported presence of sound is the distinguishing characteristic of this cluster, this feature does not appear to be linked strongly to any specific UAP shape.

Consistent with the manual analysis conducted by Powell et al. (2023), reports of objects roughly triangular in shape (assigned to Cluster 4) began to appear significantly more recently than reports of objects in nearly all other clusters. That prior work had also noted the association between triangular shaped objects and distinct red and white lighting patterns. Objects assigned statistically to the cluster comprising the highest percentage of roughly triangular objects in the current work (Cluster 4) were significantly more likely than objects in all other clusters except Cluster 7 to exhibit distinct lighting patterns, and these were most often reported to be red and white in color. Results of Powell et al. (2023) suggested that while hovering could be observed in objects of any shape, this feature was most common in triangular objects. Results of our cluster analysis differ somewhat from this conclusion. While objects in the cluster comprising the highest percentage of truly triangular UAP (Cluster 4) were in fact all noted to display hovering, we also identified a cluster consisting entirely of disc/spherical objects that also all exhibited hovering. Thus, a statistical approach to identifying UAP types based on multiple features suggests that hovering may be linked to both distinct disc/spherical and triangular shapes.

Powell et al. had observed what appeared to be two distinct types of discs, one with a dome and one without a dome, that differed substantially in size (discs without a dome being much larger). Although the current analysis used both shape and object size as clustering variables (in addition to hovering, EM effects, and sound), discs with domes were not allocated

to a single cluster. Rather, they were distributed across several clusters. Domes were most common ($\approx 19\%$) in the cluster comprised entirely of disc/spherical objects that hovered and were seen at relatively close range, with most of the remainder distributed evenly across Clusters 2, 5, and 7.

Powell et al. (2023) concluded that triangle-shaped UAP do not exhibit EM effects. Our findings that the cluster comprising the highest percentage of triangular-shaped UAP (Cluster 4) did not exhibit EM effects would be consistent with this prior work. However, our results suggested that UAP exhibiting EM effects reflected a distinct group of UAP reports rather than simply being a characteristic associated with a single shape. Nonetheless, as in this prior work, examination of object shapes in Cluster 6 (all exhibiting EM effects) suggested that discs/spheres were the most common shape associated with EM effects. As noted in the results, 97.0% of UAP exhibiting EM effects were reported to be within 2,000 feet or less from the observer. Although possible bias due to selection criteria for inclusion in this study must be considered, these findings may suggest an approximate upper limit (at least in order of magnitude) for the distance over which EM effects can be exerted.

Limitations

One aspect of this study highlights the importance of recognizing that results reflect not only the influence of the actual characteristics of witnessed objects, but also the characteristics of the reports and data sources themselves (e.g., military vs. civilian, differences in case report forms and questions asked, etc.). This distinction may account for identification of two distinct clusters (Cluster 1 vs. Cluster 2) that each were comprised entirely of disc/spherical objects. Detailed examination of the characteristics of each cluster suggest that data source issues may have contributed strongly to the separation into two clusters rather than aggregation into a single cluster. Disc-shaped objects in Cluster 2 were distinguished by observations at higher altitudes and greater distance than other clusters, whereas those in Cluster 1 were seen more often near the

ground at close distance. In addition, observations in Cluster 2 were much more likely to be made by aircraft pilots in flight during the daytime than those in Cluster 1. Hovering behavior was associated with all objects in Cluster 1 but none in Cluster 2. It is plausible that Cluster 1 and 2 reflect the same objects seen hovering nearby versus at high altitudes in rapid flight (sometimes in formation). Using the Hynek (1972) classification system, objects in Cluster 1 would appear to fall under the Close Encounter category whereas objects in Cluster 2 may largely correspond to the “Daylight Disc” category. It is also notable that cases in Cluster 2 were more likely to be older reports and frequently from military observers. It is possible that differences in the character of military versus civilian reports, the paucity of military cases after 1970, or changes in data collection procedures and data recording forms over time could also have contributed to similar disc-shaped objects being assigned to two different clusters or biased the cluster analysis results in unknown ways.

Several other potential limitations of the current work are noted. First, the identified clustering patterns and cluster characteristics may have been influenced by errors in witness reports (e.g., misperceptions, challenges in accurately assessing size and distance) (Frenda et al., 2011; Loftus & Palmer, 1974; Norman et al., 2024). The extent to which this might be true cannot be easily evaluated. Second, cluster results may have been biased by the shape classification assumptions employed in the current work. We note that preliminary analyses using a larger number of more specific shape categorizations failed to produce an adequate clustering solution. This may not be surprising given that variables with a relatively large number of categories are known to produce increased noise in cluster analysis and result in worse cluster separation and reduced silhouette values. Third, it is likely that there is systematic bias in the type of data obtained across different reporting sources that may have influenced the cluster analysis results. Fourth, the observed pattern of clustering results may have been influenced by our selection criteria that were designed to increase the likelihood that cases

included reflected truly anomalous data (e.g., multiple observers or highly trained single observers, minimum angular size of 0.15 degrees). In some cases, there was some subjectivity in judging the angular size and distance to the object that qualified a selected UAP case for inclusion in this dataset. These strict criteria were applied to select cases out of the larger pool of 100,000 UAP witness reports initially available in the Powell et al. study, and these criteria were expected to enhance the signal to noise ratio of witness report data examined in the current work. However, because of the selection criteria employed, observed frequencies of the specific UAP characteristics analyzed in this sample and the relative percentage of objects assigned to each cluster cannot be generalized to other samples. The methods used do however permit firm conclusions to be drawn regarding the existence of the UAP types identified and the broad characteristics of each.

Conclusions

Results of this study indicate that cluster analysis can extract meaningful information from high quality UAP witness report data. The clustering algorithm identified a model of statistically good quality that resulted in seven distinct clusters. Object shape was the strongest driver of clustering results, although other features also contributed. For example, two distinct clusters were characterized primarily by absence of hovering (potentially reflecting unique reporting sources) and two distinct clusters comprised objects all exhibiting either: 1) EM effects (disc/sphere or ovoid) or 2) sound (both unassociated with shape). These seven clusters were not inconsistent with the results of Powell et al., but the cluster analysis provided more detail, nuance, and class types than found in the manual analysis and resulted in new and useful insights. For example, the clustering put all UAP reports of EM effects into Cluster 6, and found that 97.0% of these UAP were reported to be within 2,000 feet or less from the observer

These findings serve as a proof of concept of the potential value of applying statistical pattern recognition techniques such as cluster analysis, finite mixture models, and machine

learning to large, high quality witness report datasets in order to advance knowledge regarding the nature of UAP. Results of this work indicate that while shape is an important contributor to classification of UAP types, presence of hovering, EM effects, and sound are all important as well. These findings argue for consideration of a multidimensional rather than a unidimensional typology of UAP.

Declaration of Interest Statement

The authors have no conflicts of interest to declare.

References

- Bruehl S, Lofland KR, Semenchuk EM, Rokicki LA, Penzien DB. Use of cluster analysis to validate IHS diagnostic criteria for migraine and tension-type headache. *Headache*. 1999; 39: 181-189.
- Chiu T, Fang D, Chen J, Wang Y, Jeris C. A robust and scalable clustering algorithm for mixed type attributes in large database environment. *Proceedings of The Seventh ACM SIGKDD International Conference on Knowledge Discovery and Data Mining - KDD '01*. New York, NY: ACM Press, 263–268, 2001.
- Everitt BS, Landau S, Leese M. *Cluster Analysis*. Taylor & Francis, 2001
- Frenda SJ, Nichols RM, Loftus EF. Current issues and advances in misinformation research. *Current Directions in Psychological Science*. 2011; 20, 20-23.
- Hubert LJ, Arabie C. Evaluation of clustering algorithms using the silhouette score. *Journal of Classification*. 1985; 2: 195-213.
- Hynek JA. *The UFO Experience : A Scientific Inquiry*. Henry Regnery Company, Chicago, 1972.
- Jain AK, Dubes RC. Cluster validation techniques. *IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence*. 1988; 10: 153-159.
- Kaufman R, Rousseeuw P J. Silhouettes: a graphical aid to the interpretation and validation of cluster analysis. *Journal of Computational and Applied Mathematics*. 1990; 20: 53-65.
- Kent P, Jensen RK, Kongsted A. A comparison of three clustering methods for finding subgroups in MRI, SMS or clinical data: SPSS TwoStep Cluster analysis, Latent Gold and SNOB. *BMC Med Res Methodol*. 2014; 14: 113.
- Loftus EF, Palmer JC. Reconstruction of automobile destruction: An example of the interaction between language and memory. *Journal of Verbal Learning & Verbal Behavior*. 1974; 13, 585–589

- Marler D. Triangular UFOs: An Estimate of the Situation. Richard Dolan Press, 2013.
- Medina RM, Brewer SC, Kirkpatrick SM. An environmental analysis of public UAP sightings and sky view potential. *Sci Rep* 2023; 13: 22213.
- Norman JF, Lewis JL, Ramirez AB, Bryant EN, Adcock P, Peterson RD. The visual perception of long outdoor distances. *Sci Rep*. 2024; 14: 3207.
- Powell R., Little S, Hancock L, Hasan L, Truong R, Kamoru T. The reported shape, size, kinematics, electromagnetic effects, and presence of sound of unidentified aerial phenomena from select reports, 1947-2016. 2023; Zenodo.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10287332>
- Rousseeuw PJ. Silhouettes: a graphical aid to the interpretation and validation of cluster analysis. *Computational and Applied Mathematics*. 1987; 20: 53–65.
- Teodorani M. A long-term scientific survey of the Hessdalen phenomenon. *Journal of Scientific Exploration*. 2004; 18: 217-251.
- Watters WA, Loeb A, Laukien F, et al. The scientific investigation of unidentified aerial phenomena (UAP) using multimodal ground-based observatories. *Journal of Astronomical Instrumentation*; 2023; 12, 2340006.

Table 1. Reported characteristics for overall sample of high quality UAP case reports (n = 216).

UAP Features	% or Median (IQR)
Shape (%):	
Disk/Round	44.0
Ovoid	20.4
Triangle/Boomerang	22.2
Cylinder	11.1
Other	2.3
Size (in feet; Median, IQR)	50 (95)
Ability to Hover (% Yes)	59.7
Associated with Sound (% Yes)	17.8
Presence of EM effects (% Yes)	16.7

Table 2. Distribution of features for UAP characteristics used in cluster analysis by assigned UAP clusters.

Clustering Variable	Cluster 1 (n = 32)	Cluster 2 (n = 37)	Cluster 3 (n = 18)	Cluster 4 (n = 41)	Cluster 5 (n = 22)	Cluster 6 (n= 36)	Cluster 7 (n = 30)
Shape (%):							
Disk/Round	100.0	100.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	47.2	30.0
Ovoid	0.0	0.0	0.0	34.1	54.5	25.0	30.0
Triangle/Boomerang/Delta	0.0	0.0	0.0	65.9	45.5	13.9	20.0
Cylinder	0.0	0.0	83.3	0.0	0.0	11.1	16.7
Other	0.0	0.0	16.7	0.0	0.0	2.8	3.3
Size (in feet; Median, IQR)	50 (54)	40 (80)	80 (204)	50 (175)	40 (63)	60 (105)	48 (53)
Ability to Hover (% Yes)	100.0	0.0	55.6	100.0	0.0	61.1	80.0
Associated with Sound (% Yes)	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	22.2	100.0
Presence of EM effects (% Yes)	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	100.0	0.0

Table 3. Other characteristics associated with cluster-derived UAP types by cluster.

Associated Characteristics	Cluster 1 (n = 32)	Cluster 2 (n = 37)	Cluster 3 (n = 18)	Cluster 4 (n = 41)	Cluster 5 (n = 22)	Cluster 6 (n = 36)	Cluster 7 (n = 30)
Day vs. Night Sighting (% Night)	48.3	23.5	66.7	91.9	57.1	50.0	76.7
Multiple Objects (% Yes)	6.3	13.5	5.6	2.4	9.1	2.8	0.0
Appears on Radar (% Yes)	3.1	24.3	11.1	4.9	4.5	11.1	0.0
Dome Present (% Yes)	18.8	10.8	0.0	0.0	9.1	2.8	6.7
Structure Present on Object (% Yes)	31.3	29.7	22.2	14.6	36.4	27.8	26.7
Metallic Appearance (% Yes)	37.5	35.1	38.9	17.1	13.6	44.4	36.7
Black Appearance (% Yes)	7.4	12.5	15.4	32.1	18.8	3.6	14.3
Distinct Lights on Object (% Yes)	34.4	8.1	27.8	68.3	13.6	27.8	63.3
If Yes, Color:							
Red	18.8	0.0	5.6	39.0	4.5	19.4	40.0
White	15.6	5.4	22.2	36.6	0.0	13.9	26.7
Blue/Purple	12.5	0.0	5.6	14.6	0.0	8.3	6.7
Green	6.3	0.0	0.0	4.9	0.0	2.8	6.7
Yellow	3.1	0.0	0.0	2.4	0.0	2.8	3.3
Light Beam Observed (% Yes)	3.1	0.0	5.6	2.4	4.5	5.6	13.3
Estimated Speed > Mach 1 (% Yes)	25.8	28.6	23.5	31.7	19.0	30.6	10.0
Estimated Acceleration > 10G (% Yes)	9.4	8.1	0.0	2.4	0.0	2.8	0.0
Estimated Distance from Observer (Median [IQR])	300 (1800)	2250 (4513)	460 (1300)	300 (900)	1200 (2238)	375 (938)	350 (781)
Estimated Altitude (in feet; Median [IQR])	100 (270)	4500 (7500)	1500 (3850)	100 (470)	1500 (17850)	200 (2115)	100 (268)
Displays Odd Movement (% Yes)*	65.6	51.4	11.1	41.5	18.2	47.2	40.0
Instant Acceleration/Deceleration (% Yes)	18.1	0.0	0.0	24.4	4.5	8.3	10.0
Instant Direction Change (% Yes)	6.3	8.1	0.0	2.4	4.5	2.8	6.7
Non-Aerodynamic (% Yes)	0.0	8.1	11.1	12.2	0.0	5.6	0.0
No Atmospheric Interaction (% Yes)	15.6	2.7	0.0	12.2	9.1	8.3	0.0
Approaches Observer (% Yes)	37.5	29.7	33.3	41.5	27.3	58.3	36.7
Active Engagement with Observer (% Yes)	9.4	8.1	11.1	14.6	13.6	22.2	10.0
Responds to Observers Actions (% Yes)	9.4	5.4	27.8	17.1	18.2	25.0	13.3
Animal Responses Noted (% Yes)	0.0	0.0	0.0	2.4	0.0	8.3	6.7

*Odd movement indicates angular, wobbling, falling leaf, zig zag, or spinning motion in flight.

Table 4. Pairwise statistical comparisons of clustering variables between identified UAP clusters.

Clustering Variables:	Significant Comparisons Across Clusters ($p < .05$)	Interpretation of Key Findings
Dominant Shape (% Yes):		
Disk/Round	Cluster 1 > 3,4,5,6,7 Cluster 2 > 3,4,5,6,7 Cluster 6 > 3,4,5 Cluster 7 > 3,4,5	-Clusters 1 and 2 more likely than others to reflect round/disc shapes.
Ovoid	Cluster 5 > 1,2,3,6,7 Cluster 7 > 3	-Cluster 5 more likely than others to be ovoid in shape.
Triangle/Boomerang	Cluster 4 > 1,2,3,6,7	-Cluster 4 more likely than others to display triangular/boomerang/delta shapes.
Cylinder	Cluster 3 > 1,2,4,5,6	-Cluster 3 more likely than others to reflect cylindrical objects.
Other	No significant differences	
Size (in feet)	No significant differences	
Ability to Hover (% Yes)	Cluster 1 > 2,3,5,6,7 Cluster 3 > 2,5 Cluster 4 > 2,3,5,6,7 Cluster 6 > 2,5 Cluster 7 > 2,5	-Disc/Round and Triangular/Boomerang/Delta shapes more likely than others to display hovering.
Presence of EM effects (% Yes)	Cluster 6 > 1,2,3,4,5,7	-Cluster 6 more likely than all others to display EM effects.
Associated with Sound (% Yes)	Cluster 6 > 1,2,3,4,5 Cluster 7 > 1,2,3,4,5,6	-Clusters 6 and 7 more likely than others to be associated with sound.

Table 5. Pairwise statistical comparisons of other UAP features between identified clusters.

UAP Features:	Significant Comparisons Across Clusters ($p < .05$)	Interpretation of Key Findings
Day vs. Night Sighting (% Night)	Cluster 1 > 2 Cluster 3 > 2 Cluster 4 > 1,2,3,5,6 Cluster 5 > 2 Cluster 6 > 2 Cluster 7 > 1,2,6	-Cluster 4 more likely than all others (except Cluster 7) to be seen at night.
Multiple Objects (% Yes)	Cluster 2 > 7	-Multiple UAP more likely in sightings assigned to Cluster 2 than Cluster 7. The latter are closer to the observer and associated with sound
Appears on Radar (% Yes)	Cluster 2 > 1,4,5,7	-Cluster 2 sightings more likely than others to be captured on radar.
Dome Present (% Yes)	Cluster 1 > 3,4,6 Cluster 2 > 4 Cluster 5 > 4	-Cluster 1 objects (all discs/spherical) more likely than most others to display a dome.
Structure Present on Object (% Yes)	Cluster 5 > 4	
Metallic Appearance (% Yes)	Cluster 1 > 4 Cluster 6 > 4,5	
Black Appearance (% Yes)	Cluster 4 > 6	Objects in Cluster 4 (e.g., triangular, boomerang) more likely to appear black than objects displaying EM effects (Cluster 6)
Distinct Lights on Object (% Yes)	Cluster 1 > 2 Cluster 4 > 1,2,3,5,6 Cluster 6 > 2 Cluster 7 > 1,2,3,5,6	-Objects in Clusters 4 and 7 more likely than others to display distinct lights.
Light Beam Observed (% Yes)	Cluster 7 > 2	

Estimated Speed > Mach 1 (% Yes)	Cluster 4 > 7 Cluster 6 > 7	<i>-Objects in Clusters 4 and 6 (i.e., triangular, EM effects) more likely to exhibit high speeds than Cluster 7 objects (with sound).</i>
Estimated Acceleration > 10G (% Yes)	No significant differences	
Estimated Distance from Observer (feet)	Cluster 2 > 1,4,6,7 Cluster 5 > 4,6	<i>-Objects in Cluster 2 seen at greater distances than others.</i>
Estimated Altitude (in feet)	Cluster 2 > 1,3,4,6,7 Cluster 3 > 1,4,7 Cluster 5 > 1,4,6,7	<i>-Objects in Cluster 2 were seen at greater altitude than other clusters.</i>
Displays Odd Movement (% Yes)	Cluster 1 > 3,4,5,7 Cluster 2 > 3,5 Cluster 4 > 3 Cluster 6 > 3,5 Cluster 7 > 3	<i>-Objects in Cluster 1 are more likely than most others to display odd movements (e.g., wobbling, falling leaf).</i>
Instant Acceleration/Deceleration (% Yes)	Cluster 1 > 2,3 Cluster 4 > 2,3,5 Cluster 7 > 2	<i>-Objects in Cluster 4 are more likely than most others to display instant acceleration/deceleration.</i>
Instant Direction Change (% Yes)	No significant differences	
Non-Aerodynamic (% Yes)	Cluster 4 > 1,7	
No Atmospheric Interaction (% Yes)	Cluster 1 > 7 Cluster 4 > 7	
Approaches Observer (% Yes)	Cluster 6 > 2,5	
Active Engagement with Observer (% Yes)	No significant differences	
Responds to Observers Actions (% Yes)	Cluster 3 > 2 Cluster 6 > 2	
Animal Responses Noted (% Yes)	No significant differences	

Figure 1.

Figure 2.

Figure Captions

Figure 1. Relative importance of UAP features for defining the identified clusters. Feature importance values in this figure are automatically generated within the two-step cluster analysis procedure and are based on a series of statistical comparisons of differences between features for each cluster, with the average $-\log_{10}$ p-value for each feature across clusters considered to be a measure of feature importance (rescaled so that the greatest observed value is 1).

Figure 2. Distribution of sighting report year across the seven clusters identified in this study. Color coding is used to portray the distribution of shape sub-types from Powell et al. (2023) for each cluster.

APPENDIX 1

Evaluation of Potential for Type I Error

To minimize the risk that results of cluster analysis reported in this study were due to Type I error, we created 30 simulated datasets each comprising 216 cases of totally random data and containing the 5 variables analyzed in the cluster analysis in the current work. All simulated datasets contained variables reflecting presence of hovering, EM effects, and presence of sound, all coded as 0/1 to indicate absence/presence as in the main dataset and reflecting equal likelihood of being coded 0 or 1. The random object shape variable was derived two ways for use in different analyses: first as a categorical variable coded 1-5 with equal likelihood of falling into any category (uniform distribution) and the second reflecting a Poisson distribution coded 1-5 weighted towards higher likelihood of disc/round or ovoid shapes as in the actual dataset. The random object size variable was also derived two ways: one as a continuous variable reflecting a randomly assigned (uniform distribution) size between 15 and 300 feet (the 10th and 90th percentiles for object size in the actual data) and the second reflecting a normal distribution with mean of 300 feet and a standard deviation of 100 feet. Examination of multiple distributions for the latter two variables was intended to capture any influence of the data distribution on results of the cluster analyses on the simulated datasets.

Results of two-step cluster analysis examining the 10 simulated (random) datasets reflecting object shape (uniform distribution), object size (uniform distribution), hovering, EM effects, and sound indicated that *none* met the criterion for a good quality clustering solution (silhouette values for each were $< .50$). See example results in Supplemental Figures 1A – 1D below. The object feature of greatest importance for determining cluster membership appeared random across these simulated datasets, with the following features all identified as being the most importance feature in at least one simulated cluster analysis: hovering, EM effects, object shape, and sound (with EM effects the most common).

To address any possible bias due to the distribution of object size, two-step cluster analysis was also used to examine the 10 simulated (random) datasets reflecting object size (normal distribution), object shape (uniform distribution), hovering, EM effects, and sound (see example results in Supplemental Figures 2A – 2D below). Results again indicated that *none* met the criterion for a good quality clustering solution (silhouette values all $< .50$). The most important feature for determining cluster membership again appeared random across these simulated datasets, with the following features all identified as the most important in at least one simulated cluster analysis: EM effects, hovering, and sound. Object shape was not identified as the most important UAP feature in cluster analyses of any of these simulated datasets.

Finally, to address possible effects of the distribution of object shape on clustering results, we also conducted two-step cluster analysis on 10 simulated (random) datasets reflecting object shape (Poisson distribution), object size (uniform distribution), hovering, EM effects, and sound (see example results in Supplemental Figures 3A – 3D below). As above, results again indicated that *none* met the criterion for a good quality clustering solution (silhouette values all $< .50$). The most important feature for determining cluster membership again appeared random across these simulated datasets, with the following features all identified as the most important in at least one simulated cluster analysis: sound, hovering, object shape, and EM effects, with presence of sound the most common feature identified as the most important UAP feature in determining clustering results. Overall, results of two-step cluster analyses on random datasets reflecting various distributional assumptions indicated that the presence of random data did not in even a single case produce a clustering solution that met the criterion of silhouette value $> .50$ necessary to indicate good clustering. Moreover, there was no evidence that the distribution of the object shape variable led to an overestimation of the importance of this variable in determining cluster results.

Supplemental Figures 1A – 1D. Example results of two-step cluster analysis examining four simulated (random) datasets reflecting object shape (uniform distribution), object size (uniform distribution), hovering, EM effects, and sound.

Figure 1A.

Figure 1B.

Figure 1C.

Figure 1D.

Model Summary

Algorithm	TwoStep
Inputs	5
Clusters	10

Cluster Quality

Predictor Importance

Supplemental Figures 2A – 2D. Example results of two-step cluster analysis examining four simulated (random) datasets reflecting object size (using a normal distribution), object shape (uniform distribution), hovering, EM effects, and sound.

Figure 2A.

Figure 2B.

Model Summary

Algorithm	TwoStep
Inputs	5
Clusters	7

Cluster Quality

Predictor Importance

Figure 2C.

Model Summary

Algorithm	TwoStep
Inputs	5
Clusters	5

Cluster Quality

Predictor Importance

Figure 2D.

Supplemental Figures 3A – 3D. Example results of two-step cluster analysis examining four simulated (random) datasets reflecting object shape (Poisson distribution), object size (uniform distribution), hovering, EM effects, and sound.

Figure 3A.

Figure 3B.

Figure 3C.

Figure 3D.

